

Genotype Analysis of Vaginal *Candida albicans* Isolates and Fluconazole Susceptibility in Tunisia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC) is a common fungal infection caused mainly by *Candida albicans*. This study aimed to determine the genotypes and subtypes of *C. albicans* responsible for VVC and to assess their susceptibility to fluconazole.

Methods: A total of 103 females referred to the Laboratory of Parasitology at the Military Hospital of Tunis for vaginal sampling were included. *C. albicans* isolates were identified using phenotypic and molecular methods. Genotyping and subtyping were performed using 25S rDNA-based and ALT-RPS-based primers, respectively. The susceptibility to fluconazole using E-test technique was made for 60 strains.

Results: Genotype B was the most prevalent (46%), predominantly subtype B2/3/4 (51%), followed by genotype A (34%) with subtype A2/3/4 (49%), and genotype C (20%) with a single subtype C3. The mean age of patients was 31 years (range: 13–74). The most common clinical sign was white leucorrhea, observed in 80% of cases. Significant correlations were found between genotypes and age group, pregnancy status, trimester, clinical signs, and culture abundance ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, sub-genotype distribution was significantly associated with pregnancy, parity, and trimester ($p < 0.05$). Fluconazole susceptibility testing revealed that 57% of strains were resistant.

Conclusion: This study identified three major *C. albicans* genotypes (A, B, and C) and ten RPS subtypes among Tunisian VVC isolates. A high rate of fluconazole resistance was observed, highlighting the need for antifungal susceptibility testing to guide effective treatment.

KEYWORDS: *Candida albicans*, genotype, antifungal susceptibility, Fluconazole

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
24 January 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC) is a common fungal infection disease of vaginal mucosa. VVC is caused by *C. albicans* in 70% to 90% of cases [1]. It is reported that about 75% of women suffer from VVC at least once in their lifetime. It affects mainly women during their childbearing years and is considered the second most common cause of vaginitis after bacterial vaginosis [2].

Clinical symptoms of VVC are nonspecific and include generally pruritus, hyperemia, vaginal discomfort, leucorrhea, burning, soreness, dyspareunia, vaginal and vulvar erythema [3]. The most common predisposing host factors are uncontrolled diabetes mellitus,

immunosuppression, pregnancy, and hormone replacement therapy [1-4]. *Candida albicans* constitute 80-90% of yeasts isolated from the vagina [1,5].

Genotyping of *C. albicans* is important in epidemiological studies. Several genotypes of *C. albicans* have been described, and PCR targeting 25S rDNA is commonly used for genotype analysis. This method allows classification into five genotypes: A (450 bp), B (840 bp), C (450 and 840 bp), D (1,080 bp), and E (1,400 bp) [6,7]. Understanding the distribution of *Candida* species and *C. albicans* genotypes is crucial for appropriate treatment, as different genotypes may exhibit variable responses to antifungal agents [8,9].

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This study aimed to determine the genotypes and subtypes of *C. albicans* responsible for VVC in Tunisian women attending the Military Hospital of Tunis and to assess their fluconazole susceptibility profile.

II. METHODS

Study population and clinical data

We included 103 females referred to the Laboratory of Parasitology at the Military Hospital of Tunis, all confirmed positive for *Candida albicans*. For each participant, clinical data were collected, including age, number of pregnancies, gestational trimester, and clinical signs.

Sample collection and phenotypic identification

Vaginal samples were examined directly and cultured on Sabouraud-Chloramphenicol medium with and without actidione. *C. albicans* isolates were identified by phenotypic and molecular methods. Phenotypic identification included chlamyospore formation on Tween agar and yeast growth on Sunflower medium.

A. PCR-ITS-RFLP identification

DNA was extracted from pure cultures. The Internal Transcribed Spacer 1 (ITS1) region was amplified as previously described [10]. Restriction digestion was performed using the enzyme MspI. Strains yielding 297 bp and 238 bp fragments were selected for further genotyping.

B. Genotyping and subgenotyping

Genotype determination was performed using 25S rDNA primers: CA-INT-L (forward) and CA-INT-R (reverse) (Table I). Subtyping based on ALT-RPS (tandem short repeat of 172 bp) was performed using primers ASDcF and pCSCR. PCR conditions for both reactions were: 50 μ L reaction containing 1.5 mM MgSO₄, 0.2 mM dNTPs, 1 U Taq DNA polymerase, 50 pmol primers, and 2 μ L DNA. Amplification cycles were 95°C for 3 min, followed by 35 cycles at 94°C for 30 s, 59°C for 30 s, 72°C for 30 s, with a final extension at 72°C for 10 min. PCR products were analyzed on 1.2% agarose gel.

C. Statistical analysis

Associations between genotypes, sub-genotypes, and clinical variables were analyzed using SPSS 22.0 software. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

D. Fluconazole susceptibility testing

Fluconazole susceptibility of 60 *C. albicans* isolates was performed using the E-test on Mueller-Hinton medium. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) were interpreted according to EUCAST 2020 guidelines: sensitive if MIC \leq 2 mg/L, resistant if MIC > 4 mg/L.

III. RESULTS

A. Phenotypic identification

Of the 103 positive samples, 72 (70%) showed positive direct examination: 38 with pseudohyphae and 34 with yeast cells. All cultures produced beige colonies on Sabouraud-

Chloramphenicol medium with and without actidione, chlamyospores on Tween agar, and yeast growth on Sunflower medium.

B. Molecular identification by PCR-RFLP

All isolates (n = 103) produced a single 535 bp band after ITS PCR. MspI restriction digestion yielded two fragments of 297 bp and 238 bp, confirming *C. albicans* identification (Figure 1). Phenotypic and molecular diagnoses were fully concordant.

C. Genotyping and subgenotyping

25S rDNA genotyping:

Genotype B was the most prevalent (46%), followed by genotype A (34%) and genotype C (20%). Genotypes D and E were not detected (Figure 2, Table II).

RPS subtyping

Five subtypes were identified among all genotypes: 2/3/4 (n=41), 3 (n=40), 2/3 (n=11), 3/4 (n=7), and 2/3/4/5 (n=4) (Figure 3). Subtype distribution according to genotype (Table III):

- **Genotype B (n=47):** B2/3/4 (51%), B2/3 (19%), B3/4 (15%), B3 (15%)
- **Genotype A (n=35):** A2/3/4 (49%), A3 (34%), A2/3/4/5 (11%), A2/3 (6%)
- **Genotype C (n=21):** C3 (100%)

D. Study population characteristics and statistical associations

Table IV summarized clinical and laboratory data of our patients and their statistical analysis according to genotypes of *Candida albicans* isolates.

The mean age was 31 years (range: 13–74). Most participants were aged 21–30 years (51%), followed by 31–40 years (41%). Genotype distribution by age: 21–30 years: genotype B (22.3%) and A (21.3%); 31–40 years: genotype C (11.6%) (p < 0.05).

Seventy-eight women (75.7%) had been pregnant at least once; 50% had at least two pregnancies. Genotype B and C were more frequent among women with \geq 2 pregnancies (23% and 11.6%, respectively, p < 0.05). Among pregnant women (n=78), genotype B was observed in 34%, A in 22.3%, and C in 19%. Most were in the third trimester (n=40, 38.8%). A significant association was observed between genotype and gestational trimester (p < 0.05).

The most frequent clinical sign was leucorrhea (61%), predominantly whitish (49.5%). Genotype A was significantly associated with whitish leucorrhea (p < 0.05). Culture abundance differed by genotype: +++ abundance was noted for genotypes B and A in 17.5% and 11.6%, respectively; genotype C showed ++ in 10.7% (p < 0.05).

Table V summarized the statistical analysis between the clinical and laboratory data according to sub-genotypes of *Candida albicans*.

Sub-genotype analysis showed:

- B2/3/4 and C3 subtypes were more frequent in pregnant women with \geq 2 pregnancies (p < 0.05)

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- B2/3/4 was predominant in the third trimester ($p < 0.05$)
- Higher culture abundance (+++) correlated with RPS subtypes 2/3/4 (45%) and 3 (35%) ($p < 0.05$); no correlation was observed for C3 except for culture abundance ($p < 0.05$)

E. Fluconazole susceptibility

Of the 60 isolates tested, 26 (43%) were sensitive and 34 (57%) resistant to fluconazole. The mean MIC for sensitive strains was 0.89 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Resistance was predominantly observed in genotypes C and A. Subtype-specific resistance: C3 (13%), B2/3/4 (11%), A3 (10%) (Tables VI–VII).

IV. DISCUSSION

Vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC) is one of the most common infections in pregnant and young women [1,12,13], with *Candida albicans* being the predominant causative species [12,14]. Our study employed ABC genotyping based on 25S rDNA, a widely used molecular method that is an important tool for epidemiological investigations [15,16].

Table VIII summarizes the genotyping and RPS subtype results from our study compared to previous reports. Our work is the first to show the dominance of genotype B (47.46%) in Tunisian women, whereas most studies report genotype A as predominant. However, Gharaghni (2021) [17] reported genotype C as the most frequent. Differences in genotype distribution may be explained by variations in clinical specimen origin, geographical location, and patient populations [16].

Genotypes D and E were not detected in our study. The absence of genotype D, corresponding to *Candida dubliniensis*, may be due to the methods used (Sunflower medium and PCR-RFLP), which are less sensitive for discriminating this species.

RPS subtyping revealed predominance of the B2/3/4 subtype, which was absent in studies by Swadagoo (2019) [11] and Amanlo (2020) [16]. These studies reported dominance of A3 and RPS3 subtypes, respectively. Moreover, our study identified combined RPS patterns (2/3/4 and 2/3/4/5) not previously reported, highlighting potential associations between genotypes, sub-genotypes, and patient characteristics such as age, physiological state, and clinical signs.

We found significant correlations between genotypes and age group, pregnancy status, trimester, clinical signs, and culture abundance. Sub-genotypes were also associated with pregnancy number and trimester. These findings contrast with Salman (2019) [20] and Xia-Dong (2008) [21], who found no significant association between genotypes and clinical parameters, but agree with Abu Baker (2012) [22], who reported significant relationships between *C. albicans* genotypes, patient age, and VVC symptoms. Such associations may be influenced by host immune status, hormonal environment during pregnancy, and the invasive potential of specific genotypes [23,24].

Regarding antifungal susceptibility, fluconazole remains the most commonly used azole for VVC treatment, with topical

therapy recommended initially (clotrimazole, ketoconazole, econazole) and oral therapy for recurrent cases (fluconazole, itraconazole) [IDSA guidelines]. In our study, 34 of 60 tested isolates (57%) were resistant to fluconazole, predominantly genotypes C and A. Subtype-specific resistance was observed in C3 (13%), B2/3/4 (11%), and A3 (10%). Overuse without medical prescription and widespread antifungal exposure may contribute to this resistance. Swadagoo (2019) [11] also reported high fluconazole resistance in genotype A (RPS A3) (Table IX), likely due to mutations in ERG genes, including ERG11.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Genotyping of *C. albicans* using 25S rDNA followed by ALT-RPS analysis identified three major genotypes (A, B, and C) and ten RPS subtypes in Tunisian VVC isolates. A high proportion of strains ($\approx 50\%$) exhibited resistance to fluconazole. Future studies will focus on elucidating the molecular mechanisms underlying this antifungal resistance and exploring novel therapeutic molecules with alternative targets.

Funding statement: No funding

Acknowledgements: None.

Ethical Approval statement: Not applicable

Data availability statement: The author(s) declare that all data are available on request

Declaration of competing interest: The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement: **Mtibaa Latifa:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing **Baccouchi Nawel:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Soudi Hana:** Data curation, Investigation, Software. **Jemli Boutheina:** Visualization, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Table I: List of PCR Primers (25SrDNA and RPS) and Expected Sizes of PCR Products [11]

Primers	Nucleotide sequences (5'-3')	Band size (pb)	25Sr DNA Type
		450	A
CA-INT-L	ATAAGGGAAGTCGGCAAATAGATCCGTAA	840	B
CA-INT-R	CCTTGGCTGTGGTTTCGCTAGATAGTAGAT	450 & 840	C
		1040	D
		1080	E

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Primers	Nucleotide sequences	Band size (pb)	RPS TYPE
		526	1
		698	2
ASDcF	TGATGAACCACATGTGCTACAAAG	870	3
Pescr	CGCCTCTATTGGTCGAGCAGTAGTC	1042	4
		1214	5
		1396	6

Table II: frequency of *C. albicans* genotypes in VVC patients

<i>C. albicans</i> genotypes	No	%
A	35	34%
B	47	46%%
C	21	20%
Total	103	100%

Table III: Analysis of *Candida albicans* isolates by 25S rDNA genotyping and RPS sub-genotyping

Genotype A (n=35)				Genotype B (n=47)				Genotype C (n=21)	Total
A3	A2\3	A2\3\4	A2\3\4\5	B3	B2\3	B3\4	B2\3\4	C3	
12	2	17	4	7	9	7	24	21	103
12%	2%	16%	4%	7%	9%	7%	23%	20%	100%

Table IV: Distribution of *Candida albicans* genotype in relation to patient's characteristic

	Genotype A		Genotype B		Genotype C		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Age interval (years)								
<21	1	1%	1	1%	0	0%	2	1.9%
21-30	22	21.3	23	22.3	8	7.7	53	51.4
31-40	9	8.7	21	20.3	12	11.6	42	40.7
41-50	1	1	1	1	0	0	2	1.9
>50	2	1.9	1	1	0	0	3	2.9
Chi-square	46.57		56.51		8.85			
P value	0.00		0.00		0.01		0.51	
Pregnancy number								
0	9	8.7	12	11.6	2	2	23	22%
1	11	10.6	11	10.6	7	6.8	29	28%
≥2	15	14.5	24	23	12	11.6	51	50%
Chi-square	1.6		6.68		7.14			
P value	0.449		0.035		0.028		0.09	
Pregnancy								
Oui	23	22.3%	35	34%	20	19%	78	75.7
Non	12	11.6%	12	11.6%	1	1%	25	24
Chi-square	1.38		4.23		13			
Pvalue	0.24		0.040		0.00		0.09	
Trimester								

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T1	9	8.7 %	10	9.7	6	5.8	25	24.2
T2	2	1.9 %	5	4.8	6	5.8	13	12.6
T3	12	11.6	20	19.4	8	7.7	40	38.8
Chi-square	8.3		10		4			
P-value	0.01		0.01		0.13		0.03	
Clinical signs								
Vulval Pruritus	5	4.8	8	7.7	9	8.7	16	15.5
Urinary burning	10	9.7	15	14.5	2	1.9	36	34.9
Leucorrhoea	24	23.3	25	24	14	13.5	63	61
<i>Whitish</i>	20	19.4	19	18.4	12	11.6	51	49.5
<i>Yellow</i>	2	1.9	4	3.8	2	1.9	8	7.7
<i>Greenish</i>	2	1.9	1	0.9	0	0	3	2.9
Chi-square	4.8		0.191		0.43			
P value	0.03		0.66		0.51		0.12	
Direct examination								
Positive Yeast	9		21		4		34	33%
Pseudofilament	17		13		8		38	36.9%
Negative	9		13		9		31	30%
Chi-square	3.65		2.7		2			
P value	0.16		0.25		0.36		0.1	
Abundance of the culture								
+	5	4.8	8	7.8	3	2.9	16	15.5
++	10	9.7	15	14.6	11	10.7	36	34.9
+++	8	7.8	18	17.5	3	2.9	29	37.8
++++	12	11.6	6	5.8	4	3.8	22	21.4
Chi-square	3.06		8.23		8.5			
P value	0.38		0.04		0.04		0.21	

Table V: Distribution of the population studies according between Sub-genotypes of *Candida albicans* and the patient's characteristics

	Sub-genotypes									Total
	A3	A2\3	A2\3\4	A2\3\4\5	B3	B2\3	B3\4	B2\3\4	C3	
Age interval (years)										
<21	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0		2
21-30	11	0	11	0	2	0	6	15	8	53
31-40	0	2	6	1	3	8	1	9	12	42
41-50	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
>50	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	4
Chi-square	8.3	ND	1.4	0.5	1.5	5.4	3.5	1.5	8.8	
P value	0.004	ND	0.22	0.7	0.6	0.02	0.059	0.22	0.01	0.09
Pregnancy number										
0	3	0	3	3	2	1	1	8	2	23
1	4	1	6	0	1	2	2	6	7	29
≥2	5	1	8	1	4	6	4	10	12	51
Chi-square	0.5	0	2.2	1	2	4.6	2	1	7.1	
P value	0.77	1	0.32	0.3	0.3	0.09	0.36	0.6	0.02	0.1
Pregnancy										
Oui	9	1	13	0	5	7	5	19	20	79
Non	3	1	4	0	2	2	2	5	1	20
Chi-square	3	0	4.7	ND	1.2	2.7	1.2	8.1	17	
Pvalue	0.08	1	0.29	ND	0.25	0.09	0.26	0.04	0.00	0.1

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Trimester										
T1	1	0	4	0	4	2	1	3	4	19
T2	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	3	4	11
T3	5	1	6	0	1	4	3	12	10	42
Chi-square	2.6	0	2	ND	1.8	2	1.6	9	4	
P-value	0.1	1	0.36	ND	0.1	0.36	0.44	0.01	0.13	0.4
Clinical signs										
Vulval Pruritus	7	2	8	2	3	5	4	8	9	48
Urinary burning	3	1	2	0	1	1	0	2	2	12
Leucorrhoea	8	2	11	3	4	7	1	13	12	61
Whitish	6	1	9	3	3	6	0	10	11	49
Yellow	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	2	8
Greenish	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	4
Chi-square	1.3	0	1.4	1	0.1	2.7	3.5	0.1	0.4	
P value	0.24	1	0.22	0.3	0.7	0.09	0.59	0.6	0.5	0.16
Direct examination										
Positive yeast	4	0	3	2	4	2	2	13	4	34
Pseudofilament	4	1	10	2	2	4	2	5	8	38
Negative	4	1	4	0	1	3	3	6	9	31
Chi-square	0.0	0	5	0	2	0.6	0.28	4.7	2	
P value	1	1	0.08	1	0.36	0.7	0.86	0.09	0.3	0.7
Abundance of the culture										
+	2	0	3	2	1	0	2	5	3	18
++	4	1	3	0	1	5	2	7	11	34
+++	2	0	5	1	4	3	2	9	3	39
++++	4	1	6	1	1	1	1	3	4	22
Chi-square	1.3	0	1.5	0.5	3.8	2.6	0.42	3.3	8.5	
P value	0.7	1	0.66	0.7	0.2	0.26	0.93	0.3	0.03	0.03

ND: not determined

Table VI: Analysis of the results of susceptibility to Fluconazole according to the 25s rDNA genotype identified

Genotype	S	R	Total
A	10	15	25
B	11	11	22
C	5	8	13
Total	26	34	60

S: sensitive; R: resistant

Table VII: Analysis of isolates resistant to Fluconazole according to the identified RPS sub-genotype

Genotype	Subgenotype					Total (N)
	3	3/4	2/3	2/3/4	2/3/4/5	
A	6		1	5	3	15
B	1	2	1	7		11
C	8					8
Total	15	2	2	12	3	34 R

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Table VIII: Comparative summary of our results and the literature of the distribution of Genotypes and sub-genotypes

ABC Genotypes											
The study/year	Isolate origin	Genotype A	Genotype B	Genotype C	Genotype D	Genotype E					
Our study 2023/	Vulvo-vaginal	35.34%	47.46%	21%	0%	0%					
[15]	Peripheral swabs	75.7%	24.3%	0%	0%	0%					
[18]	Clinical isolates	57.1%	21.9%	18.6%	1.66%	0.66%					
[19]	Oral cavity, scale, and vagina from animals	40.8%	18.5%	18.5%	0%	22.2%					
[11]	oral cavity, vagina, nails, smooth skin, urine and stools	85,4%	10.4%	4.2%	0%	0%					
[16]	Oropharyngeal	45.2%	32.3%	22.6%	0%	0%					
[17]	Vulvo-vaginal	3.9%	12.6 %	83.5%	0%	0%					
RPS Sub-genotypes											
		A3	A2/3	A2/3/4	A2/3/4/5	B3	B2/3	B3/4	B2/3/4	C3	Other sub-genotype
Our study	Vulvo-vaginal	12 %	2%	16%	4%	7%	9%	7%	23%	20%	
[11]	oral cavity, vagina, nails, smooth skin, urine and stools	40 %	14.6%	0%	0%	2.1%	5.2%	1%	0%	0%	A2(24%), A3/4(6.3%), B2 (2.1%), C2 (3.1%), C2/3 (1%)
[16]	Oropharyngeal	41.9%	3.2%	0%	0%	19.35 %	6.5%	6.5%	0%	19.35%	C2/3 (3.2%)

Table IX: Comparative summary of our results and the literature of antifungal susceptibility to Fluconazole

		A3	A2/3	A2/3/4	A2/3/4/5	B3	B2/3	B3/4	B2/3/4	C3	Total
[11]	S	6.1%	0%	ND	ND	0%	10%	0%	ND	ND	14.6%
	I	3.7%	2.4%	ND	ND	0%	10%	10%	ND	ND	11%
	R	36.6%	14.6%	ND	ND	20%	30%	0%	ND	ND	74.4%
Our study	S	5%	1.6%	10%	0%	3.3%	1.6%	3.3%	10%	8.3%	43.1%
	R	10%	1.6%	8.3%	5%	1.6%	3.3%	1.6%	11.6%	13.3%	56.3%

ND: not detected; S: sensitive; I: intermediate; R: resistant.

Figure 1: Electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel: M: size marker (100 bp); A: *Candida albicans* ITS PCR amplicons (535bp); B: two bands (297 and 238 bp) after enzymatic digestion with MspI

Figure 2: ABC genotyping profile of *Candida albicans* isolates (genotype A: 450 bp; genotype B: 840 bp; and genotype C: 450 and 840 bp); M: molecular size; N: negative control; 1-10: samples.

Figure 3: RPS subtype of *Candida albicans*; M: molecular size; N: negative control; 1-7: samples